

Orthogonal Designs for Computing the MLE of Discrete Latent Class Models in Record Linkage

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Abstract

In the context of estimating discrete latent-class models for record linkage, Winkler (1994) describes instances where sparse classifications lead to hard-to-estimate or non-estimable log-linear models. Winkler (1988) gives a blueprint proposing to expand new families of log-linear models to deal with these difficulties. Much later, Fienberg and Rinaldo (2012) develop a rigorous framework characterizing instances of log-linear models that are non-estimable in the presence of sparse contingency tables. These authors emphasize orthogonality to retrieve fragmented parameterization when log-linear models are not estimable. This approach provides a context for the blueprint described by Winkler and leads us to propose rich families of log-linear models in the record linkage situation where maximizing the nominal likelihood is difficult or impossible.

Disclaimer

Any views expressed on statistical methodology, technical or operational issues are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the U.S. Census Bureau.

1 Introduction

1.1 Likelihood Zeros

Within the subject of fully identifiable models, Fienberg and Rinaldo discuss likelihood zeros. These are cells containing observed frequencies of zero that are also not estimable, as opposed to sampling zeros which are cells containing frequencies of zero whose estimates exist and are positive. In the space of the log-odds ratio, the cell probabilities for likelihood zeros are unbounded, and so part of the MLE is not estimable. Fienberg and Rinaldo propose the extended MLE (EMLE) which recuperates the estimable part of the MLE at the cell level. Methodology and software (Friedlander 2016) are available to identify likelihood zeros. Similar issues surface when trying to maximize the likelihood of latent

class models using the EM algorithm. In this situation, some of the expected cells of the full contingency table computed at each E-step become arbitrarily close to zero. We call such cells limiting zeros.

1.2 Fellegi-Sunter: A Latent Class Model

The Fellegi-Sunter (F-S) Model (1969) for record linkage is a multinomial latent-class log-linear model (Goodman 1974) involving binary manifest variables and a binary class identifier. The binary manifest variables codify whether two records being compared agree over given various comparison fields characterizing entities -often persons or businesses- such as last name, first name, age, address, etc. The records being compared are retrieved from one or more files. The class identifier characterizes the nature of each record pair. The characterization is a “true match” if the two records describe the same entity -person, business, etc. Otherwise, it is “false match”. Unfortunately, the status identifier is unobserved, so the model is not identifiable. The analyst is responsible for identifying a maximum for the likelihood and labeling the parameters of the process consistently with respect to status. We will be more explicit on this.

The basic assumption of the Fellegi-Sunter model is that comparisons over each field are independent conditional on the status of each pair. Accordingly, the log-model includes only interactions between match status and the outcome of any one comparison over a matching variable. Despite the simplicity of the model non-identifiability persists. Additional issues may emerge where a local maximum cannot be found.

1.3 Boundary Estimates

One indication that a local maximum may not exist is that attempts to maximize the likelihood lead to parameter estimates very close to the boundary. In fact, a sequence of approximations may not converge to a limit within an open ball near the boundary. At the cell level, the E step of the Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm produces limiting zeros. Galindo Garre and Vermunt (2006), and Wurpts and Geiser (2014) discuss “boundary estimates” manifest when limiting zeros lead to conditional probabilities of the latent class model arbitrarily close to 0 or 1. This problem is noted by other authors -see for example Kang et al. (2014). Such boundary estimates render the estimates unusable as probabilistic measurements.

1.4 Existing Solutions to Deal with Boundary Estimates

To prevent estimates from getting too close to the boundary. Galindo Garre and Vermunt (2006) suggest introducing prior information through the specification of formal prior distributions. When maximizing the likelihood through the EM algorithm, the prior is integrated during the M step. Rather than formally specifying a prior distribution, Schafer (2021) proposes introducing prior

information adding small numbers -called “nuggets”- to the full table before each M step, thereby blunting the emergence of limiting zeros.

1.5 A New Approach: An Analytical Solution

In the context of identifiable log-linear models, Fienberg and Rinaldo provide tools to extract the most information from log-linear likelihood in the presence of likelihood zeros and compute the estimable part of the MLE along with its degrees of freedom. The situation becomes more complex in the context of unidentifiable (latent) class models when the full table is not observed. We work in the EM algorithm paradigm (Dempster Laird Rubin 1977). In that paradigm, an initial guess is made for the MLE and the E-step reconstructs the full table based on the observed data and the last approximation of the MLE. Each E step is followed by an M step, a likelihood-maximizing attempt based on the full table. We attempt to maximize the likelihood conditional on the last E-step using the Newton-Raphson procedure in the context of a Poisson general linear model.

When a pattern of zeros persistently shows up on the full table after the E-step while the parameter approximation continue to approach the boundary, it may be possible to compute an orthogonal projection of the parameter that captures most of the information available from the likelihood and is also orthogonal relative to the parametric subspace underlying the patterns of zero. We suggest an alternative to specifying a prior distribution: identifying estimable models with reduced degrees of freedom based on orthogonal projections of the F-S model away from the linear subspaces involving non-estimable parameters.

We show that orthogonally decomposing the parameter space according to the axis of the natural F-S parameters can lead to log-linear models that compensates for the non-estimable parameters and replace them by geometric averages of the estimable parameters. This approach is in fact an application of the method proposed by Winkler (1988) in the linear algebra of the log-odd ratios defining general linear models in the Poisson family.

1.6 Outline

The outline of the rest of this paper is as follows. Section 2 recalls the definition of the Fellegi-Sunter model in the ANOVA-like notation and exploits that notation to derive the conditional models and submodels related to the orthogonalization approach of the paper. We illustrate those same concepts in the context of the linear algebra in the log-odd ratios allowing us to formulate F-S and its sub-model as general linear models, which can readily be fitted using GLM packages and the Poisson family. Section 3 reviews the F-S decision rule and Section 4 the EM algorithm in the context of the F-S model and submodels expressed as 2 independent Poisson distributions. Section 6 illustrates our proposed methodology and compares it to existing methods on fictitious data to complete the proof of concept.

2 Background

2.1 Fellegi-Sunter as a Multinomial

We first give a general representation of the log-linear model supporting the Fellegi-Sunter model. We assume that we are attempting to match records from two different databases that have c fields in common for that purpose. For each record pair, we define the comparison vector $\mathbf{f} = (f_1, \dots, f_c)$, where $f_i = 1$ when the two records of a pair do not agree on field i and $f_i = 2$ when the two records agree on field i . Let s denote the (unobservable) match status of the pair so that $s = 1$ if two records do not characterize the same entity and $s = 2$ when the two records characterize the same entity. Let $x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}$ denote the counts of the record-pair comparison patterns f_1, \dots, f_c with match status s . Let \mathbf{x}_s denote the vector that concatenates all of the $x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}$ in lexicographic order of the f_i 's, where f_1 varies fastest and f_c varies slowest. Let \mathbf{x} be the vector that concatenates \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 .

For the purpose of setting the foundations and developing the methodology, we assume that we observe \mathbf{x}_s , a realization of the multinomial vector \mathbf{X}_s with elements $X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}$, for $s = 1, 2$. The associated multinomial cell probabilities are $P_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}$. Following the same scheme as for \mathbf{X}_s , \mathbf{P} is the vector of the cell probabilities. Its likelihood is:

$$L_{\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{P}) = \prod_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s=1}^2 (P_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s})^{x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}} \quad \mathbf{P} \in \Omega. \quad (1)$$

What characterizes the Fellegi-Sunter conditional independence model is the structure of the constraint Ω on \mathbf{P} on the log scale. We use the notation of Thibaudeau (1993), which exploits the ANOVA-style notation of Bishop, Holland and Fienberg (1974, p. 33), to explicitly represent Ω . See Schafer (2021) for a discussion on how this notation differs from a genuine ANOVA in several ways. This notation allows for compact expressions for many log-linear models and naturally leads to the construction of multinomial design matrices that can serve as inputs to general linear model software packages, such as glm in R. We show in the paper how to construct a multinomial design matrix. The parameter space Ω for the Fellegi-Sunter model is defined by

$$\log(P_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}) = \mu + \alpha_s + \sum_{i=1}^c \left(\delta_{f_i}^{(i)} + \eta_{f_i, s}^{(i)} \right) \quad (2)$$

and

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = \sum_{f_i \in \{1,2\}} \delta_{f_i}^{(i)} = \sum_{f_i \in \{1,2\}} \eta_{f_i,s}^{(i)} = \sum_{s \in \{1,2\}} \eta_{f_i,s}^{(i)} = 0 \quad (3)$$

for $i = 1 \dots c$

and

$$\sum_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s=1}^2 P_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} = 1. \quad (4)$$

Here, α_s represents the main effect of the status of the pair, δ_{f_i} is the main effect of comparison field i , $\eta_{f_i,s}$ is the interaction effect between field i and status, and μ can be construed as a normalizing constant enforcing (4). In general, (2) - (4) leaves $2c + 1$ free parameters or degrees of freedom in the F-S model. Our intent in laying down (2) - (4) is to provide the foundations to exploit the F-S model as a General Linear Model, and will culminate in the specification of 2 independent Poisson regressions together representing the F-S model.

2.2 Conditional Multinomials

As pointed out by Larsen and Rubin (2001), (2) - (4) defines a mixture of 2 multinomials conditional on the true match status, s . To derive analytical solutions to solve estimability problems, it will pay off to center on the design of the 2 elements of the mixture. We are careful not to change the conditional independence basic architecture of each element in the F-S model. Let $T_s = \sum_{f_1, \dots, f_c=1}^2 X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}$ be the total of \mathbf{X}_s and $T = T_1 + T_2$. Conditional on $T_1 = t_1$ and $T_2 = t_2$, \mathbf{X}_1 and \mathbf{X}_2 are independent multinomial random variables with totals t_1 and t_2 , each generated by c independent comparison fields as derived in Appendix A. For example, let $c = 3$. From (38), the log-linear model conditional on $S = s$ is

$$\log(P_{f_1, f_2, f_3 | s}) = \nu^* + \beta_{f_1 | s}^{(1)} + \beta_{f_2 | s}^{(2)} + \beta_{f_3 | s}^{(3)} \quad (5)$$

where $f_1, f_2, f_3, s = 1, 2$. The following identifiability constraints apply:

$$\beta_{2 | s}^{(1)} = -\beta_{1 | s}^{(1)} ; \beta_{2 | s}^{(2)} = -\beta_{1 | s}^{(2)} ; \beta_{2 | s}^{(3)} = -\beta_{1 | s}^{(3)} \quad (6)$$

while ν^* is the normalization constant such that $\sum_{f_1, f_2, f_3=1}^2 P_{f_1, f_2, f_3 | s} = 1$.

Consider the two submodels of (5, 6) induced by the following additional constraints:

$$\beta_{1 | s}^{(1)} = -(\beta_{1 | s}^{(2)} + \beta_{1 | s}^{(3)}) / 2 \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_1^{(1)} = (\beta_{1 | s}^{(2)} + \beta_{1 | s}^{(3)}) / 2 \quad (8)$$

By swapping $\beta_{1|s}^{(1)}$ with $\beta_{1|s}^{(2)}$ in (7)-(8), and then similarly swapping $\beta_{1|s}^{(1)}$ with $\beta_{1|s}^{(3)}$, we define a total of 6 submodels of (5). Eqs. (7)-(8) represent orthogonal projections of the parameter space of the model (5, 6) in the space of log-odd ratios away from the axis of $\beta_{1|s}^{(1)}$, as shown in the next subsection.

Two properties of an orthogonal projections are that it is guaranteed to be a submodel and under that submodel the estimates of the parameters orthogonalized against are functions of the projection. In that sense, under the submodel the nominal parameters share the degrees of freedom of the projection. Ideally, the linear subspace of the log-odd ratios orthogonalized against fully contains the subspace preventing convergence to a bonafide MLE. In practice, achieving such an ideal configuration may be impossible without jeopardizing the multinomial nature of F-S. Instead, we attempt to identify the best orthogonal projection in the sense that it recuperates as much as possible of the information surviving part of the MLE and does not introduce ancillary information.

It is beyond the scope of the paper to give a complete discussion of the geometric and topological issues involved in attempting to rigorously identify and define only partially estimable MLEs. We will focus instead on its linear algebraic underpinnings to motivate our approach. We refer to Fienberg and Rinaldo (2012), Friedlander (2016) and Sharifi Far, Papathomas and King (2019) for more insight.

There are additional models that emerge naturally from our expansions. To simplify the presentation, we focus on (7), (8), and their variants. Each submodel reduces the degrees of freedom of the model (5) without changing the structure of the original model. Note in each case that the parameterization is arbitrary in the sense that it can be expressed involving any pair of the 3 nominal parameters $\beta_{1|s}^{(1)}$, $\beta_{1|s}^{(2)}$ and $\beta_{1|s}^{(3)}$. In each case, these 3 nominal parameters share the remaining 2 degrees of freedom though one of the 12 proposed sharing arrangements.

2.3 Multinomial Design Matrices

In this section, we lay down the foundations to extend the F-S multinomial to a general linear model in the Poisson family. We exploit the log-odd ratio to later integrate the two conditional multinomials of the form (5) into two independent Poisson models.

For this exercise, we continue to assume we can observe $S = s$ for each pair of records being compared and there is no ambiguity when computing $x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}$. Later, we discuss methods to handle the typical situation when s is no longer available and $x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}$ must be estimated. Define the conditional log-odd ratios given $S = s$ as follows:

$$\phi_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s} = \log \left(\frac{P_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}}{P_{1, \dots, 1, s}} \right). \quad (9)$$

We call category $1, \dots, 1$ in (9) the *reference category* or the *baseline category*.

Let

$$\phi_s = [\phi_{1,\dots,1|s} \quad \dots \quad \phi_{2,\dots,2|s}]^t \quad (10)$$

For this paper, we will focus on the case where there are $c = 3$ fields. Then, we can write

$$\phi_s = D_s \lambda \quad (11)$$

where

$$D_s = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^t \quad (12)$$

and

$$\lambda = \left[-2\beta_{1|s}^{(1)} - 2\beta_{1|s}^{(2)} - 2\beta_{1|s}^{(3)} \right] \quad (13)$$

We call D_s in (12) a multinomial design matrix for the multinomial in (5). D_s provides a labeling for the categories of the multinomial. We can define a new multinomial design matrix and a new labeling by changing the reference category. For instance:

$$\phi_{f_1,\dots,f_c|s}^* = \log \left(\frac{P_{f_1,\dots,f_c,s}}{P_{2,1,\dots,1,s}} \right). \quad (14)$$

Then the baseline is $2, 1, \dots, 1$ and we have

$$\phi_s^* = D_s^* \lambda^* \quad (15)$$

where

$$D_s^* = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^t \quad (16)$$

and

$$\lambda^* = \left[2\beta_{1|s}^{(1)} - 2\beta_{1|s}^{(2)} - 2\beta_{1|s}^{(3)} \right]. \quad (17)$$

D_s and D_s^* are two multinomial design matrices for the same multinomial (5). D_s and D_s^* are also two labelings of the same multinomial. The 0's and 1's in the first column are swapped, meaning the labels “high” and “low” are swapped, but the model is the same.

In general, if there are N variables, there are 2^N distinct labelings corresponding to the 2^N possible baselines. All the labelings can be derived by changing the baseline (reference category) when computing the log-odd ratios. The choice of labeling does not matter when specifying the design matrix for the nominal F-S model for the purpose of estimating a Poisson general linear model using a software package, such as `glm` in R. We will discuss how to do this in more details in the next section.

2.4 Orthogonal Projections

We can also derive multinomial design matrices for the submodels (7) - (8). They are respectively

$$\mathbf{D}^{orth1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & -2 & -1 & 0 & 1 & -2 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & -2 & -1 & -2 & -1 \end{bmatrix}^t \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{D}^{orth2} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & -2 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -2 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 & -2 & -1 & -2 \end{bmatrix}^t. \quad (19)$$

The column space of \mathbf{D}^{orth1} in (18) is orthogonal to the first column of \mathbf{D}_s in (12), while the column space of \mathbf{D}^{orth2} in (19) is orthogonal to the first column of \mathbf{D}_s in (16). Note that \mathbf{D}^{orth1} and \mathbf{D}^{orth2} have different baselines, as indicated by the rows of zeros. They also represent different models, unlike \mathbf{D}_s and \mathbf{D}_s^* which represent the same model.

2.5 Fellegi-Sunter as a Poisson GLM

In the previous section, we use multinomial design matrices to characterize the distributions of \mathbf{X}_1 and \mathbf{X}_2 conditional on their respective totals T_1 and T_2 assuming they are known. Based on (2), T_1 and T_2 are in fact binomial random variables conditional on a mixture probability π_1 (Larsen and Rubin 2001) and on the grand total $T_1 + T_2$. We enrich the basic Fellegi-Sunter model by positing $T \sim \text{Poisson}(\exp(\lambda))$, where $\lambda = \log(\mathbb{E}[T])$, thereby increasing the number of degrees of freedom in the model from $2c + 1$ to $2c + 2$.

In turn, we have $T_s \sim \text{Poisson}(\exp(\lambda_s))$, where $\lambda_1 = \lambda + \log(\pi_1)$ is the log of expected number of true non-matches and $\lambda_2 = \lambda + \log(\pi_2)$ is the log of expected number of true matches, where $\pi_2 = 1 - \pi_1$. We can now frame the F-S model as 2 independent Poisson general linear models. As such, we have the tools to solve the associated estimation issues. In our new set-up, \mathbf{X}_s is a vector of independent Poisson random variables. Let

$$\xi_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} = \log(\mathbb{E}[X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}]) \quad (20)$$

$$= \log(\mathbb{E}[T_s] P_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s}) \quad (21)$$

$$= \log(P_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s}) + \lambda_s \quad (22)$$

Keeping the same reference category as in (9) and from (22) we have

$$\xi_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} - \xi_{1, \dots, 1, s} = \phi_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s}. \quad (23)$$

So

$$\xi_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} = \phi_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} + \xi_{1, \dots, 1, s} \quad (24)$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_s = \boldsymbol{\phi}_s + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \xi_{1, \dots, 1, s} \quad (25)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_s = [\xi_{1,1,\dots,1,s} \ \dots \ \xi_{2,2,\dots,2,s}]^t. \quad (26)$$

We make use of multinomial design matrices to define a Poisson GLM for F-S. We have

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_s \in \mathcal{CS}\{\boldsymbol{\Delta}_s\} \quad s = 1, 2. \quad (27)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\Delta}_s = [\boldsymbol{D}_s \quad | \quad \mathbf{1}] \quad (28)$$

is a Poisson design matrix and \boldsymbol{D}_s is given in (12). Note that \boldsymbol{D}_s can be replaced by \boldsymbol{D}_s^* in (16) or any other matrix labelling of the multinomial in (5) and still (27) continues to hold.

To attempt to resolve issues of non-estimability we can substitute an orthogonally projected multinomial design matrix, such as \boldsymbol{D}^{orth1} from (18) for \boldsymbol{D}_s in (28). This reduces the dimensionality of the nominal F-S model while staying in the multinomial family and maintaining conditional independence. In all cases, in the language of Schafer (2021) we obtain a pair of independent Poissons acting as a surrogate for a multinomial. We review the F-S rule and the EM algorithm in light of the new models in the next 2 sections.

3 The Fellegi Sunter Decision Rule

3.1 Fellegi-Sunter Weights

The cornerstone of the Fellegi-Sunter decision rule is the estimation of

$$\log \left(\frac{\hat{P}_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s=2}}{\hat{P}_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s=1}} \right). \quad (29)$$

We can use

$$\hat{\xi}_{f_1, \dots, f_c, 2} - \hat{\xi}_{f_1, \dots, f_c, 1} = \log \left(\frac{\hat{P}_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s=2}}{\hat{P}_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s=1}} \right) + \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 \quad (30)$$

as a proxy for (29), where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\xi}}$ is the MLE through Poisson regression.

4 EM Algorithm for Estimation under Aggregated Counts

The problem, of course, is that \boldsymbol{x} is not observed by the analyst. The analyst observes \boldsymbol{x}_+ , where $x_{f_1, \dots, f_n, +} = x_{f_1, \dots, f_n, 1} + x_{f_1, \dots, f_n, 2}$. The frequency agreement patterns are aggregated over the status, which is then unidentifiable. The EM algorithm can be used to iteratively reapportion $x_{f_1, \dots, f_n, +}$ between $x_{f_1, \dots, f_n, 1}$ and $x_{f_1, \dots, f_n, 2}$. We call the limiting iteration of \boldsymbol{x} the limiting conditional table, or simply the conditional table. We assume the conditional table exists whenever the sequence of approximation converges.

The E-Step reapportions the aggregated counts between the two Poisson regressions defined in (28) based on the last values of the estimates. We have

$$x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}^{t(t+1)} = \left(\frac{\hat{\mathbb{E}} [X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} | \boldsymbol{\xi}^{tt}]}{\hat{\mathbb{E}} [X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, 1} | \boldsymbol{\xi}^{tt}] + \hat{\mathbb{E}} [X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, 2} | \boldsymbol{\xi}^{tt}]} \right) x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, +} \quad (31)$$

where $\boldsymbol{x}^{t(t+1)}$ is the conditional table at step $t + 1$ of the EM algorithm. In the case $c = 3$, the M step is simply to fit two independent Poisson regressions $\boldsymbol{x}_s^{t(t+1)}$, $s = 1, 2$ for two additional Poisson regressions based on the matrix $\boldsymbol{\Delta}_s$ in (28). However, problems arise when $\hat{\mathbb{E}} [X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} | \boldsymbol{x}^{tt}] \rightarrow 0$ when $t \rightarrow \infty$. A necessary condition for the existence of the MLE is

$$\liminf_t \hat{\mathbb{E}} [X_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s} | \boldsymbol{\xi}^{tt}] > 0. \quad (32)$$

Note that (32) does not preclude the existence of zero cells in the observed table \boldsymbol{x} , or in the imputed table \boldsymbol{x}^{tt} at any time t . What (32) guards against is the existence of *likelihood zeros* in the limiting conditional table \boldsymbol{x}^{tt} , as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

5 Example of a Boundary Estimate

5.1 Simulation and Illustration

We refer to the notation of Larsen and Rubin (2001) to express latent class log linear models as conditional independence models. Table 2 gives the seed parameters of our simulation. Table 1 gives the instance of a table of counts we use for purpose of illustration. Table 2 shows the estimates produced by an attempt to maximize the nominal F-S likelihood and reveals a boundary estimate for $\pi_{1|2}$. We identify the underlying limiting zeros and show how the methods discussed can compensate for the associated estimation pitfalls.

5.2 Limiting Zeros and Orthogonalization

Table 1 displays the limiting zeros (marked with a *) emerging on the conditional table as the EM algorithm is iterated. Note the pattern of the limiting zeros is in perfect synch with the boundary estimate and leads to non-estimability. Both orthogonal projection and cvam are designed to eliminate boundary estimates by preventing the emergence of limiting zeros.

5.3 Orthogonal Projections

The Model 1 and Model 2 rows in Table 2 give results under models in (7) and (8) respectively. Note the design matrix of Model 2 in (19) is orthogonal to the exposed subspace underlying the limiting zeros and leading to the boundary estimate in the sense that it is the pattern of the limiting zero that irremediably leads to $1 - \pi_{1|s} \rightarrow 0$.

By contrast, the design matrix of Model 1 in (19) is designed to repair the situation $\pi_{1|s} \rightarrow 0$. Another way to get insight is to examine the following explicit formula. Under Model 1, we have

$$\pi_{1|s} = \frac{\sqrt{(1 - \pi_{2|s})(1 - \pi_{3|s})}}{\sqrt{\pi_{2|s}\pi_{3|s}} + \sqrt{(1 - \pi_{2|s})(1 - \pi_{3|s})}}. \quad (33)$$

Under Model 2, we have:

$$\pi_{1|s} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi_{2|s}\pi_{3|s}}}{\sqrt{\pi_{2|s}\pi_{3|s}} + \sqrt{(1 - \pi_{2|s})(1 - \pi_{3|s})}}. \quad (34)$$

Eqs. (33) and (34) give a good sense on what orthogonal projections are. Note the effect is different than bluntly dropping $\pi_{1|s}$ in the nominal log-linear model (5), which is tantamount to setting $\pi_{1|s} = .5$ (Schafer 2021). A Bayesian perspective in the sense of looking at the parameters as if they are random variable helps make sense of (33) and (34). Depending on the pattern of the limiting zeros, the linear subspace chosen to orthogonally project against, $\pi_{1|s}$ is negatively correlated (33) or positively correlated (34) with both $\pi_{2|s}$ and $\pi_{3|s}$. Model 3 and Model 4 are similar to Model 1 and Model 2 except $\pi_{2|s}$ is associated to the subspace being orthogonalized against and $\pi_{1|s}, \pi_{3|s}$ are the survivors. Similar arrangements exist for Models 5, 6 where $\pi_{3|s}$ is orthogonalized against.

Note that in Table 2, Models 2, 4, 6 lead to estimates closer to the partial MLE of the nominal model. We retain Model 2 as the best candidate because of the linear algebraic reason mentioned above. Table 1 gives the estimates for F-S at the cell level along with the partial MLE, including the limited zeros, cvam and truth from the simulation.

5.4 cvam

cvam (Schafer 2021) is a regularization R package design specifically to correct boundary estimates in latent class analysis so a full classification can be produced. Tables 1 and 2 display the results for this illustration. From a statistical modeling perspective, one important difference is that the model estimated by cvam does not lose any degrees of freedom despite the presence of non-estimable cells and/or parameters. This is made possible by including what amounts to prior information, but not through a formal prior distribution, as proposed by Galindo Garre and Vermunt, but by slightly incrementing each cell of the expected table after each E-step. These small increments can be construed as providing a “tutor” to guide the likelihood maximization. In this limited exercise, cvam is fully functional and competitive.

5.5 Precision

According to the Fellegi-Sunter rule, if a model is correct, we can expect the scores to rank the cells of the observed table in decreasing order of proportion

Table 1: Cell-Level Estimates

s	x_{111s}	x_{211s}	x_{121s}	x_{221s}	x_{112s}	x_{212s}	x_{122s}	x_{222s}
Full Table								
1	96957	934	977	17	994	13	5	0
2	0	0	0	2	0	4	3	94
Matching Frequencies								
Aggregated	96957	934	977	19	994	17	8	94
$x_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}^{i(t+1)}, t = 20000$, (from EM Algorithm)								
1	96957	933.2	977.0	9.384	994.0	9.548	8.000	.09601
2	0*	.7630	0*	9.615	0*	7.451	0*	93.90
Conditional EMLE								
1	96958	933.2	975.0	9.384	992.0	9.548	9.975	.09601
2	0*	.7630	0*	9.615	0*	7.451	0*	93.90
Orthogonal Projection (2)								
1	96957	938.5	973.5	9.423	992.7	9.609	9.967	.09648
2	.01119	.2275	.3524	7.1604	.1468	2.983	4.622	93.90
cvam								
1	96959	933.2	974.9	9.383	991.9	9.547	9.974	.09599
2	.0009944	.7733	.01243	9.666	.009657	7.510	.1207	93.88

Table 2: Conditional Probabilities

Marginal Prob	π_2	$\pi_{1 2}$	$\pi_{2 2}$	$\pi_{3 2}$	$\pi_{1 1}$	$\pi_{2 1}$	$\pi_{3 1}$
Simulation	.001	.99	.95	.99	.01	.01	.01
Cond EMLE	.001117	1	.9264	.9071	.009533	.009955	.01012
Orthogonal Projection							
1	.002509	.4713	.5363	.5209	.009182	.009508	.009698
2*	.001094	.9530	.9692	.9291	.009586	.009940	.01013
3	.002416	.6157	.4287	.5255	.009026	.009671	.009735
4	.001108	.9831	.9580	.8990	.009555	.009938	.01013
5	.002394	.6168	.5420	.4200	.009036	.009557	.009852
6	.001107	.9757	.9115	.9532	.009561	.009973	.010101
cvam	.0011	.9987	.9257	.9066	.0095	.0100	.0101

of true matches among the record pairs. We consider the 8 observed cells for all 8 comparison patterns. Each cell may contain true matches and true non-matches. We can plot the cumulative precision obtained by ranking the cells by the F-S scores. This is equivalent to ranking the observed cells by decreasing order of the estimated proportion of true matches.

Figure 1 shows the cumulative precision of Models 2, 4, 6, and cvam, as well as for the “ideal” or perfect method, for the simulated data. Figure 2 zooms in on the first four cells. The ideal method correctly ranks the observed cells by decreasing proportion of true matches (Table 1) leading to the highest possible cumulative precision. All the methods identify the cell with the highest proportion (1) of true matches and rank it first. Accordingly, the cumulative precision after one cell is perfect for all the methods since that cell includes only matches. Likewise, all the methods rank the 4 cells containing matches before those not containing matches and again they have the same cumulative distribution (.75) as the ideal method. Between cell 1 and cell 4 in their respective rankings, all the methods fall short of the ideal ranking.

Intuitively, all methods choose the records that match on all fields first, and then the records that match on exactly two fields, in some order. All methods then choose the records that match on one or fewer fields in the same order.

6 Discussion

A likelihood maximum may not exist for log-linear models based on a sparse contingency table. In particular, a latent class log-linear likelihood may not

Figure 1: Full Ordering of Cells

Figure 2: Zoomed-in Section of First Four Cells of Figure 1

have a local maximum that can be identified, resulting in boundary estimates. The complexity of non-identifiability of such a likelihood is a natural deterrent to trying to identify analytical solutions to these problems.

In the case of record linkage and the Fellegi-Sunter rule, ad-hoc substitutes (Winkler 1994) are proposed. They may be functional, but scoring all of the matching patterns is impossible. The problem can worsen in high dimensions with multiple boundary estimates. General numerical approaches are proposed. They involve introducing slight perturbations of the likelihood in the form of prior information. `cvam` introduces certain regularization concepts that allow the analyst to derive estimates from their nominal model in the face of obstacles making standard maximum likelihood maximization impossible. As such, regularization has become a popular alternative to avoid the costly efforts of specialized modeling in these situations.

We propose an approach attempting to exploit the concepts of orthogonality in log-linear parametric subspaces introduced by Fienberg and Rinaldo. While our approach involves modeling, it can be automated in the case of popular latent class models, such as Fellegi-Sunter. In the case of conditional independent latent-class multinomial models, orthogonal projections are easily derived in any number of dimensions and for any number of boundary estimates. Computational power is critical to construct many projections and identify the right one in high-dimensional problems. We focus on record linkage and Fellegi-Sunter. Then, our approach as described here is systematic. Regardless of the solution, we think that identifying an estimable MLE can add rigor.

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A Multinomial Log-Linear Constraints

From (2), we have

$$\log(P_{f_1, \dots, f_c, s}) = \omega_s + \sum_{i=1}^c \beta_{f_i|s}^{(i)} \quad (35)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{f_i|1}^{(i)} &= \delta_{f_i}^{(i)} + \eta_{f_i,1}^{(i)} \\ \beta_{f_i|2}^{(i)} &= \delta_{f_i}^{(i)} - \eta_{f_i,1}^{(i)} \\ \omega_1 &= \mu + \alpha_1 \\ \omega_2 &= \mu - \alpha_1 \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Therefore, the log-linear model characterizing the conditional distribution of \mathbf{X}_s conditional on $S = s$ is

$$\log(P_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s}) = \nu_s + \sum_{i=1}^c \beta_{f_i | s}^{(i)} \quad (37)$$

where $\nu_s = \omega_s + \omega_s^*$ and ω_s^* is a normalizing term and can be expressed strictly as a function of the $\beta_{f_i | s}^{(i)}$'s and ω_s .

We derive the design matrix associated to the conditional odd ratios given $S = s$. From (35),

$$\phi_{f_1, \dots, f_c | s} = \sum_{i=1}^c \gamma_{f_i | s}^{(i)} \quad (38)$$

where

$$\gamma_{f_i | s}^{(i)} = \begin{cases} 0 & f_i = 1 \\ -2\beta_{1 | s}^{(i)} & f_i = 2 \end{cases} \cdot \quad (39)$$

Therefore,

$$\phi_s = \mathbf{D}_s \begin{bmatrix} -2\beta_{1 | s}^{(1)} \\ \vdots \\ -2\beta_{1 | s}^{(c)} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (40)$$

The columns of \mathbf{D}_s are alternating segments of zeros and ones of length 2^i , where $i = 1, \dots, c$ indicates the comparison field. \mathbf{D}_s is a valid design matrix as its first row is zero. $\mathcal{CS}\{\mathbf{D}_s\}$ fully characterizes the parameter space of ϕ_s .

B R Programs

We developed two software modules in R. These are early versions and we plan on expanding the functionality.

The first module computes the orthogonal projection of a standard multinomial design matrix under conditional independence from any column. The module can also compute joint orthogonal projections from any pair or larger collection of columns in the design matrix. The design matrix is $2^N \times N$, where N is the number of identifiers. The module also creates variants of the orthogonal projection by swapping their rows to account for boundary estimates that are either 0 or 1. At present, the module does this swapping only for projections away from single columns or a pair of columns. Accordingly, the module creates 2 variants when orthogonalizing against a single column and 4 variants against a pair of columns. Therefore, since there are N identifiers, the module selects every individual column and every pair of columns, creating a total of $2N$ and $4N(N - 1)/2$, respectively.

The second module reads all the projection matrices created by the first module. For each matrix, it runs the EM algorithm through iterated Poisson regressions so each cell of the observed table can be assigned a score consistent with the Fellegi-Sunter rule. It also computes the conditional probabilities.